

1 **AFP (Alpha fetoprotein) is expressed in pluripotent stem cells and silenced during commitment to**
2 **the TE.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of alpha
9 fetoprotein (AFP) as a lineage commitment marker in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Yin, Y., Lim, Y.K., Salto-Tellez, M., Ng, S.C., Lin, C.S. and Lim, S.K., 2002. AFP+, ESC-derived
12 cells engraft and differentiate into hepatocytes in vivo. *Stem Cells*, 20(4), pp.338-346.